

Terpenoids: Part XXIX. Synthesis of *dl-trans* Veticadinene

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Synthesis of (\pm)*trans* veticadinene has been achieved. 1-keto-4-carbomethoxy-6-methyl *trans*-decalin on alkaline hydrolysis yields 1-keto-4-carboxy-6-methyl-*trans*-decalin which is converted to 1-keto-6-methyl-decalyl-4-carboxylic acid chloride, when refluxed with thionyl chloride in benzene. The acid chloride with cadmium dimethyl furnished 1-keto-4-acetyl-6-methyl *trans*-decalin. The latter on submission to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane affords the terpenic hydrocarbon.

Veticadinene (I), a bicyclosesquiterpene, does not occur in nature but is obtained as a dehydration product of the tertiary alcohol, veticadinol (II), which has been isolated from congovetiver oil¹. The stereochemistry of the above compound has not been determined. The literature does not record any synthesis of veticadinene, though we have reported² recently a clean synthesis of (II) with stereochemistry as shown in (III).

The present studies are directed towards an unambiguous synthesis of (\pm)-veticadinene with stereochemistry as shown in (IV). The various steps in the synthesis are depicted as below:

1-keto-4-carbomethoxy-6-methyl-*trans*-decalin(V), the starting material, was obtained as reported earlier². It was hydrolysed with potassium hydroxide to give in 87% yield,

1. Chiurdoglu and Delsemme, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, **55**, 18795.
2. Vig, Matta, Gurdip Singh and Inder Raj, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 605.

the corresponding keto acid (VI), which was characterised through infrared absorption spectrum which showed peaks at 3350-2500 (associated OH), 1755-1710 (carbonyl of acid and ketone), 1378 and 1460 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$). The acid (VI) in anhydrous benzene,

on refluxing with thionyl chloride³ afforded in 90% yield. The acid chloride (VII) was converted to 1-keto-4-acetyl-6-methyl-*trans*-decalin (VIII) through cadmium dimethyl reagent in 58 per cent yield. It was characterised through infrared absorption spectrum showing peaks at 1720 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1460 and 1378 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$). The diketone (VIII), when submitted to Wittig's reaction⁴ with methyl triphenylphosphonium iodide in the presence of methyl sulphanyl carbanion according to the conditions of Corey and co-workers, afforded methylene-4-isopropenyl-6-methyl-*trans*-decalin (veticadinene) in 66% yield. It was purified by chromatography over alumina by eluting with petroleum ether.

Its I.R. absorption spectrum showed peaks at 1645, 890, 1780 (overtone) $\left. \begin{matrix} \text{R}_1 \\ \text{R}_2 \end{matrix} \right\} \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$ and 1460, 1380 ($-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$) cm^{-1} . Lit.¹ reports the peaks at 1649, 1775 and 888 cm^{-1} . (We could not get a sample of veticadinene obtained by Belgian workers for comparison with our synthesised product).

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. spectra were recorded in Beckman IR-5 with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film.

1-Keto-4-carbethoxy-6-methyl-decalin(*trans*) (V). This compound was prepared exactly according to the procedure described by Vig et al.²

1-Keto-4-carboxy-6-methyl-decalin (*trans*) (VI). The ester (V) (6 g.) was taken in a solution of potassium hydroxide (10%, 30 ml.) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hours.

3. Cason and Prout, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 46.

4. Greenwald, Chaykovsky and Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.

The contents after cooling were extracted with ether in order to remove the unhydrolysed ester (V). The aqueous portion was acidified and extracted with ether. After the removal of ether, the residual oil was vacuum distilled to furnish (VI) b.p. 185°/5-6 mm. η_D^{38} 1.530 (Calc' for $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$, 68.57; H, 8.57%, Found, C, 68.43; H, 8.49%).

1-Keto-6-methyl-decalyl-4-carboxylic acid chloride (VII): A mixture of the acid (VI) (4.39 g.), thionyl chloride (3.3 g.) and dry benzene (35 ml.) was heated under reflux over a water bath for 3 hrs. Benzene was removed and the residue on distillation afforded the acid chloride (VII), b.p. 148-50°/5-6 mm, yield 4.2 g. (90%) η_D^{38} 1.4995 (Calc' for $C_{12}H_{17}O_2Cl$: C, 63.02; H, 7.44; Found: C, 63.25; H, 7.38; Cl, 15.92%).

1-Keto-4-acetyl-decalin (trans) (VIII). To the Grignard reagent, prepared from clean dry magnesium turnings (0.84 g.), methyl iodide (2.7 g.) and dry ether (140 ml.), was introduced with stirring, anhydrous cadmium chloride (2.92 g.) in small lots. The contents being cooled during the addition. After the addition, the reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 3 hrs. and then the solvent was completely replaced by anhydrous benzene (40 ml.) (thiophene free) as usual. The acid chloride (VII) (4.0 g.) was added with stirring at such a rate as to maintain benzene at a gentle reflux. After the addition, the contents were refluxed and stirred for 3 hrs. The mixture was decomposed with ice-cold sulphuric acid. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted twice with ether. The combined extract was made acid free as usual and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residual material distilled under reduced pressure to obtain (VIII) as light material, b.p. 148-50°/5-6 mm, yield 2.1 g (58.3%) η_D^{38} 1.4990. 2:4-Dinitrophenyl-hydrazone derivative after crystallisation through acetic acid melts at 140°. (Calc' for $C_{25}H_{28}O_8N_8$: N, 19.71, Found: N, 19.60%).

1-Methyl-4-isopropenyl-6-methyl decalin (trans) (IV): A solution of methyl sulphinyll carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.18 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (4 ml.). The solution was cooled and stirred during the addition of methyl triphenyl-phosphoniumiodide (2.92 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (8 ml.), when the reddish colour of methylene-phosphorane was produced. After stirring at room temperature for 15 minutes, 1.5 g. of ketone (VIII) in tetrahydrofuran (8 ml.) was added and stirring continued for 2 hrs. at 50° under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into cold water. The organic material was taken up in petroleum ether (40-60°) and ether extract was washed thrice with cold water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over alumina eluted with petroleum ether (40-60°). The purified product was subsequently distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 100°/5 mm. yield, 1.0 g. (69%) η_D^{38} 1.4915. (Anal. Calc'd for $C_{15}H_{24}$: C, 88.23; H, 11.7%, Found C, 88.2; H, 11.73%).

One of the authors (K. L. M.) is thankful to C.S.I.R. for the award of Senior Scholarship.